

PREPREG COMPOSITES IN THE NAUTICAL INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Preimpregnated reinforcements (prepregs) in the nautical industry represent an opportunity for naval construction and an alternative method of fabricating composite structures. These prepregs include fibres, resins, their hardeners and a certain number of additives. One may consider them to be semi-products. Their characteristics allow the highest levels of performance and reliability to be attained.

keywords: prepreg, laminate, high performance, nautical, economics.

PREPREGS

FABRICATION OF A COMPOSITE LAMINATE

Single ply prepregs, usually delivered in the form of a roll, are cut using a template and stacked in the desired sequence. The stack is then polymerised (temperature & pressure cycle) to obtain the laminate; then finished (flash removed, accessories etc).

CHARACTERISTICS OF A PREPREG

- total weight
- resin type
- reinforcement type
- lifetime at ambient temperature
- storage possibilities
- laminate mechanical properties
- fabrication processes

ANALYSIS OF THE NEEDS OF BOATYARDS AND NAUTICAL CONSTRUCTION.

- FABRICATION OF LARGE COMPONENTS

Boatyards must have the capacity to produce components of large dimensions: hulls, decks, gear, appendages etc.

- SEARCH FOR HIGH PERFORMANCE MATERIALS

- Reliability

- Safety

- Resistance

 - to fatigue loading

 - to a marine environment

 - to impact

 - to osmosis

- Lighter structures & the same properties

e.g. a gain of 100 Dg on the mast allows 500 Kg to be gained on the ballast. A gain of 600 Kg leads to lower buoyancy requirements.

- PRODUCTIVITY, EASE OF MANUFACTURE, AND REPRODUCIBILITY

- IMPROVEMENT OF HYGIENE AND SAFETY DURING MANUFACTURE

- COMPETITIVE COSTS

The boatyard equipment must be accessible and meet profitability criteria.

USE OF PREPREGS IN NAVAL CONSTRUCTION: THE RESPONSE TO THE DEMANDS OF THE NAUTICAL INDUSTRY.

Prepregs first appeared in the nautical industry around 1975. Since then there has been a first popularisation of the "prepreg", (from preimpregnated fibres) and products have been developed and adapted for this market.

FABRICATION OF STRUCTURAL COMPONENTS OF LARGE DIMENSIONS

The epoxy resin systems have brought a first response to the design load requirements by their superior mechanical properties. The M10 resin system developed by Brochier S.A./Ciba Geigy composites, is particularly well suited

- to the fabrication of thick composite components,

- to low temperature manufacture (around 80° C)

Figure 3 shows a viscosity-temperature curve, and Figure 4 shows schematically the vacuum bag process.

ADVANTAGES OF PREPREGS

The use of prepreg to produce high performance composites brings:

- higher laminate quality

- more homogeneous material

- more homogeneous material

The quality control performed by the preimpregnator throughout the production guarantees high reliability and quasi-constant mechanical values for the laminates.

The M10 resin system is characterised by:

- high flow which favours a high fibre volume fraction by elimination of excess resin
- good fatigue behaviour
- good moisture resistance. The moisture pick-up should be reduced to 1 or 2 % with the new M10 resin systems
- a good temperature resistance (Tg after moulding of 127°C)

Choice of reinforcement. The flexibility of the impregnation processes used by Brochier SA (transfer, "rake", full bath), allow a range of prepregs with different reinforcements and fabrics from 50 to 2000 g/m². The prepregs are available on fabrics (balanced, unidirectional), cloth, tape, UD, bundles.

EXAMPLES

- The use of carbon fibre prepregs for masts brings rigidity weight gain and low energy dispersion.

- Aramid fibre prepregs are often used for hulls as they enable structures to be lighter and offer improved impact and degradation resistance.

- Glass fibre prepregs are used for thick, impact resistant structures at a reasonable cost.

THE USE OF PREPREGS FAVOURS AND IMPROVEMENT IN PRODUCTIVITY AND RELIABLE MANUFACTURE.

Tooling:

- temperature behaviour of tooling: about 80°C,
- evolution towards more economical tooling (wood/foam) with reduction in cure temperature towards 75°C.

Fabrication:

- easy manual or automatic cutting (two protective films)
- exceptional life at ambient temperature (60 days at 25°C)
- easy lay-up, drape, tack conserved (resin system M10)
- evolution of adherence according to the component.
- superior adherence for vertical lay-up (resin system M9)

The lay-up of prepregs, without addition of resin, may be reduced to the following operations:

- compacting, in vacuum bags or press,
- use of a large oven (temperature control)
- cure/polymerisation: the flexibility of resin systems M10/M9 allows polymerisation at 82°C for 12 to 15 hours or a polymerisation at 120°C for 30 minutes (or higher temperature).

Note: Tests are currently nearing completion on a low temperature 75°C system. This system should have an out-life of 2 to 3 weeks at ambient temperature.

PREPREGS: A RESPONSE TO HYGIENE AND SAFETY CONDITIONS

In comparison to the so-called "wet lay-up", prepregs offer advantages in manufacture:

- no solvents
- no odours

and these reduce the costly installation of ventilation systems.

In addition, Brochier SA/Ciba Geigy Composites have recently invested in a new impregnation system by transfer without solvent, within a policy of respect for the environment.

MAINTAINING COST COMPETITIVE

The gains in productivity, to which may be added a tendency for lower material costs, allowing more profitable use of equipment, make this technology accessible to the nautical industry and to naval shipyards.

- Cost of traditional procedure:
Cost of polyester resin + cost of glass reinforcement + transformation costs.
- Cost of prepreg process:
Cost of prepreg+ transformation costs.

The economic assessment reveals that the costs of the transformed material are similar for the two cases.

The impact of the use of prepregs on the nautical industry is seen in:

- more performant products,
- a high added value on the final product,
- a "high technology" image.

THE CONTRIBUTION OF THE PREIMPREGNATOR BROCHIER SA TO THE NAUTICAL INDUSTRY.

The expertise of Brochier SA/ Ciba Geigy Composites in the nautical industry enables the necessary technical and commercial support to be available to boatyards for the use of preimpregnated products:

- on-site demonstration
- collaborative tests
- optimisation of products with respect to design requirements.

Brochier proposes a range of prepregs VICOTEX® adapted to:

- monolithic structures.
- sandwich structures NOMEX®, AEROWEB® honeycomb, PVC foam, PU foam (the latter technique was the object of studies in collaboration with boatyards).